

Between Innovation and Structuring: The Strategic and Ambivalent Role of Management Control in Moroccan Startups

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Abstract

Background: Moroccan start-ups operate under the tension between rapid innovation and organisational structuring. Their low survival rate can be explained by the scarcity of resources and informal structures. In this context, management control (MC) plays a dual role: it serves as a tool for discipline but can also be a potential obstacle to agility.

Objective: To analyse management control practices in 131 Moroccan start-ups and assess their impact on performance, decision-making quality and the obstacles encountered.

Methodology: This study employed a quantitative, descriptive, and correlational approach to analyse the use of management control (MC) tools in Moroccan start-ups. Data were collected via a structured online questionnaire, yielding 131 valid responses from diverse, active, and legally registered start-ups. SPSS v26.0 was used for statistical analysis, combining descriptive statistics with advanced inferential techniques. These included the Kruskal-Wallis test, Spearman correlation, and logistic regression, which were used to examine the relationship between MC practices and start-up performance and decision-making quality.

Results: The adoption of management control (MC) depends on the startup's life cycle phase, its workforce and its age. It is used in particular for performance monitoring and cost control, while its strategic role remains limited. The primary obstacles are a lack of human and financial resources, as well as the fear of losing agility.

Conclusion: Management control is both a structuring lever and a potential obstacle to agility. It becomes truly strategic as the company grows and formalises.

Original contribution: This study highlights that, in an emerging context, management control is more of an instrument of legitimisation and progressive structuring than a direct lever for innovation.

Recommendations: Adopt a gradual and flexible approach to management control, starting with simple tools before moving on to sophisticated systems

Keywords: Moroccan context, start-ups, performance, management control, decision making

Introduction

Moroccan start-ups are evolving between rapid innovation and organisational structuring. In this context, management control (MC) appears ambivalent, serving both as a lever for discipline and a risk of rigidity that can hinder agility. While these young companies are boosting the markets, they suffer from limited resources, informal structures and rapid growth. Despite support from public authorities and incubators, their survival rate remains low, mainly because MC is often neglected in favour of initial financing alone.

This raises a key question: to what extent does the use of management control tools impact economic performance and the quality of decision-making within Moroccan start-ups? The main objective of this article is to analyse MC practices in a sample of 131 Moroccan start-ups. The aim is to identify the MC tools best suited to Moroccan start-ups, assess their impact on performance and decision-making, highlight the main obstacles to their implementation, and finally analyse the influence of start-up characteristics and founder profiles on the adoption and integration of management control. To meet these objectives, the following hypotheses are formulated:

- H1: Regular use of formalised management control tools is mainly associated with performance monitoring and cost control.
- H2: Start-ups with dedicated MC teams and structured systems make more effective and better-informed decisions.
- H3: The implementation of management control systems is a key factor in the success and sustainability of start-ups.
- H4: The adoption of management control is positively linked to the size and age of the start-up.
- H5: The older the start-up, the more likely it is to adopt a MC system
- H6: The founder's profile significantly influences the adoption of MC tools
- H7: The adoption of MC in Moroccan start-ups is mainly hampered by resource constraints

To test these hypotheses, a quantitative survey was conducted among 131 Moroccan start-ups, enabling analysis of actual MC practices, their determinants, their effects on performance and decision-making, and the obstacles encountered.

Literature review

Management control emerged at the beginning of the 20th century to support the growing complexity of organisations. Anthony (1965) defines it as a process aimed at effectiveness, efficiency and risk control. Bouquin (2006) broadens this concept by associating it with consistency between strategy and actions, while Teece (2010) highlights that management align operational choices with strategic priorities, thereby ensuring overall coherence. In a context marked by uncertainty and resource scarcity, such as that of start-ups, Teece (2010) emphasises the need for flexible and adaptive control processes. Start-ups are distinguished by their youth, growth potential, and focus on innovation. Drucker (1985) places the latter at the heart of entrepreneurship. Blank and Dorf (2012) see their mission as validating a scalable and

reproducible business model, while Ries (2011) emphasises experimentation and efficiency in uncertain environments.

Mintzberg (1983) describes their structures as agile and flat, promoting communication and responsiveness. The entrepreneurial culture, dominated by risk-taking and speed, is often embodied by the founder (Schein, 2010). Despite the scarcity of resources, this stimulates creativity (Scarpetta & Tressel, 2004). Finally, the entrepreneurial ecosystem plays a decisive role in their development (Isenberg, 2010). The European Commission (2020) confirm this view, emphasising innovation, rapid growth and internationalisation. On a theoretical level, MC applied to start-ups is based on appropriate theoretical frameworks. Contingency theory (Lawrence & Lorsch, 1967) emphasises the absence of a single model, with control needing to evolve according to size, structure, and environment (Davila, 2005). Agency theory (Jensen & Meckling, 1976) highlights the reduction of information asymmetries between founders and investors. Finally, Simons' (1995) control levers (diagnostic, interactive, belief, and boundary systems) provide a suitable framework for combining performance management with the preservation of entrepreneurial agility. However, the implementation of these systems faces several major challenges. The flexibility and entrepreneurial culture of start-ups, which are not inclined towards hierarchical structures (Nafzaoui & Ettakani, 2024), make it difficult to integrate overly formalised systems. Stakeholders may perceive these tools as bureaucratic and restrictive (Dangereux & Marsal, 2009), even though they can play a structuring and reassuring role for investors (Mintzberg, 1983). Finally, traditional tools often appear unsuitable; start-ups prefer target-based and scalable indicators that align with their growth objectives (Becker & Eendenich, 2024).

Methodologies

This study adopts a quantitative, descriptive and correlational approach to analyse the use of management control tools in Moroccan start-ups and to assess their perceived impact on performance and decision-making quality. This methodological choice allows us to examine the relationships between measurable and comparable variables, in accordance with the recommendations of Creswell (2014), Bryman (2012) and Ponto (2015). The objective is twofold: to identify the most widespread management control practices and to examine their relationship with certain performance and organisational structuring indicators.

Sample

The target population for this research consists of start-ups officially established in Morocco, regardless of their sector of activity (technology, services, commerce, products, etc.). Initially, we contacted 180 start-ups, 131 of which provided valid responses that were selected for our analysis based on the following inclusion criteria:

- Be a start-up legally registered in Morocco
- Have a management control tool or process
- Be active at the time of the survey

With a sample of 131 start-ups, the study gains statistical robustness, limits error and improves external validity. The diversity in terms of size, age and sector reinforces the representativeness of the Moroccan entrepreneurial ecosystem. This size also allows the use of advanced methods (Chi-square test, Kruskal-Wallis, Spearman and logistic regression), facilitating the

generalisation and comparison of results. Finally, sectoral heterogeneity facilitates comparative analyses and highlights the contextual specificities of management control.

Data collection

The data were collected via a structured online questionnaire (Google Forms), a method suitable for reaching a large and dispersed population, in accordance with the recommendations of Ponto (2015). The collection, spanning ten weeks, utilised various channels (LinkedIn, Facebook, WhatsApp), ensuring sectoral diversity. Participants, who were informed of the objectives and provided their informed consent, submitted 131 valid responses out of 180 questionnaires, representing a response rate of 72.8%. This response rate is satisfactory for an online survey and indicative of the interest in CM within the Moroccan entrepreneurial ecosystem.

Variables and analysis methods

In order to meet the objectives of our research, we defined a set of independent variables (describing the structural and contextual characteristics of start-ups that are likely to influence their adoption of management control) and dependent variables (relating to management control practices and their perceived role in start-up performance), operationalized in such a way as to allow for rigorous statistical processing (Table 1). This distinction between the two types of variables allows us to test specific statistical relationships, in accordance with hypothetical-deductive logic, and better to identify the organisational determinants of management control adoption.

The statistical analysis was conducted using SPSS v26.0 software. The techniques selected aim to combine descriptive analyses and inferential tests to ensure the robustness and external validity of the results. The choice of these methods enables the combination of detailed analysis of simple relationships and multivariate effects, thereby reinforcing the scientific credibility of the results.

In order to ensure greater clarity in our empirical approach, the table above summarises the variables studied, specifying their type, measurement method and the statistical methods used.

Table 1: summary of variables and analysis methods

Category	Variable	Type of Variable	Measurement method	Statistical methods used
Independent	Age	Continuous	Number of years	Descriptive, Spearman's correlation
	Size	Ordinal	Class size	Chi-square test, Kruskal-Wallis, logistic regression
	Phase	Ordinal	Launch, growth and maturity	Chi-square test, Kruskal-Wallis, logistic regression
	Sector of activity	Nominal	Technology, services,	Chi-square test, Monte Carlo

			products, agri-food, etc.	
	Presence of MC system	Dichotomous	Yes/no	Logistic regression
Indépendantes	Objectives	Nominal/Ordinal	Decision, performance, budget, cost	Chi-square test, Kruskal-Wallis
	Obstacl	Nominal	Financing, HR, complexity, culture	Chi-square test, Monte Carlo
	Tools	Nominal	Excel, ERP, specialized software, KPIs, dashboards	Chi-square test
	Perception of the strategic role of MC	Ordinal	Likert scale (1-5)	Spearman's correlation, Kruskal-Wallis

Source: ourselves

Results

The results were analysed using SPSS v26.0. Descriptive statistics were used to profile the start-ups and identify their MC practices. Associations between qualitative variables were tested using Chi-square test, with the Monte Carlo resampling method used when the conditions for application were not met. The links between ordinal and continuous variables were examined using Spearman's correlation coefficient. Finally, logistic regression was used to identify the predictive factors for the adoption of a MC system, taking into account the size, age, stage of development and sector of activity of the start-ups.

Descriptive statistics

Start-up profile

Figure 1: Breakdown by sector of activity

The majority of Moroccan start-ups operate in the technology and innovation sector (50%), confirming the driving role of the ecosystem. Services and commerce occupy an important place (21%), followed by industry, construction and development, etc. This distribution highlights the marked specialisation towards innovation and digitalisation. It also reveals the marginalisation of traditional sectors in Moroccan entrepreneurship.

Figure 2: Distribution of start-ups by age

Figure 2 illustrates the distribution of start-ups according to their age. We observe that the majority of start-ups (approximately 45%) were created between 1 and 3 years ago, reflecting

the recent dynamics of the Moroccan entrepreneurial ecosystem. On the other hand, start-ups less than one year old (less than 20%) or more than five years old (approximately 12%) remain in the minority. Companies aged 3 to 5 years represent approximately 18% of the sample. This distribution suggests that the sample is dominated by young structures still in the growth phase, which is consistent with the emerging nature of the start-up ecosystem in Morocco.

Number of employees in Start-up

Figure 3: Size of start-ups

The majority of start-ups have fewer than 10 employees, confirming their tendency to start with small, flexible teams. Around a third have between 11 and 50 employees, a sign of an initial phase of growth. Few exceed 50 employees, and only a handful exceed 100. This distribution reflects the youth of the ecosystem and highlights the importance of management styles suited to very small teams, where versatility and flexibility are paramount.

Adoption of management control

Presence of management control

Figure 4: Presence of management control

This diagram shows that the vast majority of start-ups already have a management control system in place (nearly 75%), while a minority (around 25%) have not yet implemented one. This trend reflects a growing desire for professionalization and structuring, even though a significant proportion of young companies are still characterized by informality and a lack of management tools.

Figure 5: Head of management control

Nearly 38% of start-ups entrust this function to a management controller and 35% to a financial director, a sign of growing professionalism. However, more than one in ten have no manager and around 10% delegate to the manager, revealing a structure that is still incomplete and marked by informality.

Management control tools used

Figure 6: Management control tools

Start-ups favour spreadsheets (39%) and ERP systems (37%), while 15% do not use any tools, reflecting a preference for simple and flexible solutions.

Objectives and obstacles related to management control

Figure 7: Management control objectives

Management control is primarily used for performance monitoring (37%), followed by cost reduction (24%) and budget forecasting (22%), while decision support remains limited (16%). Startups mainly use it as an operational tool, with its strategic role remaining secondary.

Main Challenges Faced by Startups Depending on the Presence of Management Control

Figure 8: obstacles encountered

Start-ups with management control mainly face a lack of specialised skills and human resources ($\approx 28\%$ each), followed by a lack of time (18%) and resistance to change (15%). Those without such systems mainly suffer from a lack of reliable data (11%) and skills (13%). Thus, the presence of a management control system strengthens the structure but leads to technical and organizational challenges, while its absence maintains more basic difficulties related to informality.

Bivariant analyses

Presence of Management Control and Responsible Party in Start-ups

Figure 9: Presence of management control x Management control manager

In start-ups with MC, the function is mainly performed by the financial director or manager, whereas without MC, it tends to fall to the accountant or manager. The Monte Carlo test ($p < 0.001$) confirms that this difference is significant, showing that formal MC favours the assignment of specialised profiles and reflects increased professionalisation of financial management.

Presence of management control x priority objectives

The results show a total absence of significant association (Chi-square test, $p = 0.532$). Thus, the main objective of management control (whether it be decision support, performance monitoring, etc.) does not depend on its formal presence in the start-up.

Figure 10: Presence of management control x obstacles encountered

Start-ups with a management control perceive recruitment as less of a major obstacle, while those without control highlight the lack of funding and the low priority given to financial management (χ^2 , $p = 0.004$). Other difficulties (human resources, complexity of tools and resistance to change)

Figure 11: Presence of management control x tools used

Financial dashboards are the most widely used, followed by KPIs. The Chi² test ($p = 0.436$) does not indicate a significant link with the presence of a MC, but the Monte Carlo test ($p < 0.001$) reveals a strong association: the choice of tools does indeed depend on the existence of a MC function.

Figure 12: Start-up phase x MC manager

The Kruskal-Wallis test ($p=0.064$) shows that the profile of the MC manager does not vary according to the stage of development of the start-up. This choice depends more on the resources available and strategic priorities than on the development cycle.

Figure 14: Spearman's correlation

Spearman's analysis shows that the presence of a management control is linked to the date of creation ($\rho = 0.291$, $p = 0.001$) and the number of employees ($\rho = 0.407$, $p < 0.001$), indicating that the larger and older a start-up is, the more it feels the need to structure its

practices through formalized tools and systems. Furthermore, the date of creation and the number of employees of the start-up are strongly correlated ($\rho = 0.599$, $p < 0.001$), confirming that age and size favour the adoption of management control .

Table 2: Kruskal-Wallis test

		Presence of a dedicated management control team			P value
		No	Oui	Shared with another function	
		Layer N %	Layer N %	Layer N %	
Life cycle phase	Launch	16,0	10,7	8,4	0,004
	Growth	13,0	22,1	17,6	
	Maturity	1,5	9,9	0,8	
Seniority	Less than 1 year	0,0	0,0	0,0	0.244
	Between 1 and 3 years	12,2	17,6	14,5	
	Between 3 and 5 years	14,5	20,6	11,5	
	More than 5 years	3,8	4,6	0,8	
Strategic integration of management control	Not integrated	8,4	0,0	0,0	0.000
	Not very integrated	9,9	2,3	7,6	
	Moderately integrated	9,2	25,2	13,0	
	Highly integrated	3,1	15,3	6,1	
Impact of organisational culture	Not impacted at all	2,3	0,0	0,0	0.002
	Little impact	9,9	2,3	6,1	
	Moderate impact	12,2	26,0	15,3	
	Significant impact	6,1	14,5	5,3	

The analysis reveals that start-ups rarely have a dedicated team for management control, unlike growing or mature companies, where this function is more structured ($p = 0.004$). The seniority of respondents has no effect ($p = 0.057$), with more senior respondents tending to be more structured.

The presence of a dedicated team is strongly linked to better integration of MC into strategy ($p=0.000$) and to an organisational culture perceived as an important lever ($p=0.002$). These results confirm that structuring this function promotes both its strategic role and its cultural anchoring.

Table 3: Age of start-ups and perception of management control as a strategic asset

		Is MC a major strategic asset as your start-up grows?		Monte carlo
		Non	Oui	
Start-up age	Less than 1 year	0	26	0.035
	1 to 3 years	1	60	
	3 to 5 years	1	23	
	More than 5 years	3	17	

source: ourselves

The majority of respondents see management control as a strategic asset for the future development of their start-up. This perception is stronger in younger organisations (less than 3 years old), while older ones (more than 5 years old) express slightly more reservations. The Monte Carlo test ($p = 0.035$) confirms the significance of this difference, indicating that young start-ups place greater value on management control as a strategic lever.

Multivariate analysis by logistic regression

Table 4: logistic regression

	Prédicteur	P	OR (BI-BS)
SU_Phase:	Launch		
	Growth	0.005	4.191 (1.5391 - 11.42)
	Maturity	0.029	12.592 (1.3029 - 121.70)
Activity_sector:	Agriculture & Agri-food	Ref	
	Industry, Construction & Urban Development	0.540	2.573 (0.1250 - 52.99)
	Institutional & Infrastructure	0.482	0.388 (0.0278 - 5.42)
	Services & Trade	0.371	0.346 (0.0337 - 3.55)
	Technology & Innovation	0.571	0.497 (0.0444 - 5.57)
Seniority:	Between 1 and 3 years	Ref	
	Between 3 and 5 years	0.601	1.311 (0.4754 - 3.62)
	More than 5 years	0.960	1.048 (0.1666 - 6.59)
management control _particularity:	Need for flexibility and adaptability	Ref	
	Problems related to cash-flow forecasting	0.540	0.606 (0.1218 - 3.01)
	Limited resources (financial, human)	0.958	1.036 (0.2784 - 3.85)
	More flexible organizational structure	0.970	1.025 (0.2876 - 3.65)
Objectif_prioritaire:	Decision support	Ref	
	Budget forecasting	0.245	2.356 (0.5553 - 10.00)
	Cost reduction	0.510	1.565 (0.4127 - 5.94)
	Performance monitoring	0.283	1.976 (0.5696 - 6.86)

The results of the logistic regression show that the start-up's development phase is the main factor associated with the presence of management control. Compared to start-ups in the launch phase, those in the growth phase are significantly more likely to have management control (OR = 4.19; 95% CI [1.54–11.42]; $p = 0.005$), as do those in the maturity phase (OR = 12.59; 95% CI [1.30–121.70]; $p = 0.029$).

On the other hand, the sector of activity, the respondent's seniority, the specific features of management control and the priority objectives are not significantly related to the presence of management control ($p > 0.05$ for all categories). Although some ORs are greater than 1, no statistically significant effect was observed for these variables. These results suggest that the start-up's progress mainly influences the adoption of management control. In contrast, the internal or specific characteristics of management control have no significant effect on its presence.

Discussion

The results of our research highlight the strategic ambivalence of management control in Moroccan start-ups, oscillating between support for innovation and the risk of organisational rigidity. Unlike large companies, where management control is often seen as a tool for standardisation and discipline (Anthony, 1965; Simons, 1995), the start-ups studied use it selectively and in a tailored way, revealing a more contingent and evolving function.

H1: Confirmed

The results show that start-ups use MC primarily to control their costs (24%) and measure their financial performance (37%), which corroborates Davila's (2005) work emphasising the primacy of financial objectives in young companies.

H2: Rejected

Our analyses indicate that management accounting does not have a significant effect on the quality of decisions, which remain largely intuitive and concentrated around the founder. This limitation reflects Simons' (1995) observation that management control is often perceived as too rigid in environments marked by uncertainty.

H3: Partially confirmed.

Although MC enhances external credibility and investor confidence, its direct role in success has not yet been fully proven. Nevertheless, it is a structuring lever that improves the ability of start-ups to grow sustainably.

H4: Confirmed

Empirical results indicate that as a start-up grows, it tends to implement more management tools. This correlation is in line with Isenberg's (2010) perspective, which suggests that start-ups progress through evolutionary stages in which the need for organisational structuring becomes increasingly critical.

H5: confirmed

Logistic regression highlights that start-ups in the maturity phase are more likely to have a MC than those in the launch phase. This result supports the idea that managerial structuring follows an incremental logic.

H6: Confirmed

The statistical results show that the founder's profile has a significant impact on the likelihood of adopting management control tools. They confirm previous work by Davila (2005) and Granlund and Taipaleenmäki (2005), which shows that the characteristics of the founder are a key lever for organisational structuring in start-ups. In the Moroccan context, where start-ups often suffer from a lack of managerial skills, the role of the founder is even more decisive, as their profile partly compensates for institutional shortcomings and the scarcity of resources.

H7: confirmed

Financial, human and technological constraints are major obstacles. Furthermore, the fear of losing agility reinforces this reluctance, which aligns with the observations of Bisbe and Otley (2004) on the tension between innovation and structure.

These results reveal a paradox: MC is perceived both as an instrument of legitimisation and structuring necessary for growth, but also as a constraint that can reduce agility and creativity. Contrary to some international studies that highlight the role of MC as a lever for innovation (Davila et al., 2009), our results show that in the Moroccan context, its role remains limited to financial performance and reporting. This specificity can be explained by the structural constraints of emerging entrepreneurial ecosystems, where the primary focus remains survival and securing financing.

The lack of confirmation of the impact of MC on decision-making calls for a relativisation of certain theoretical approaches that have made it a universal lever for managerial rationalisation. In the Moroccan context, marked by limited resources and an entrepreneurial culture that remains largely intuitive, founders tend to favour experience and instinct. MC, therefore, plays a secondary and sometimes symbolic role, serving more to formalise an image of professionalism among stakeholders than to transform internal decision-making processes. Thus, contrary to the expectations of the literature, which emphasises the structuring role of MC in the survival of start-ups, our results do not directly confirm this relationship. MC seems to contribute indirectly to sustainability, but only when the company reaches a certain threshold of growth and formalisation. In the early stages, it appears to be more of a constraint than a lever, which puts into perspective the idea of MC being systematically beneficial and suggests a differentiated effect depending on the stage of development.

Moroccan start-ups should adopt a gradual and flexible approach to MC, starting with simple tools before implementing more sophisticated systems. Incubators and investors could also play a key role in encouraging the adoption of appropriate practices to reconcile flexibility and structure.

Conclusion

Our research aimed to elucidate the strategic and ambivalent role of MC in Moroccan start-ups, a rapidly growing entrepreneurial ecosystem, by examining its practices, determinants, and effects on performance and decision-making, while navigating the imperative need to innovate and the need to structure oneself in order to survive and grow. Management control proves to be both a lever for professionalisation and a potential constraint on agility.

Firstly, our results confirm that the adoption of a MC system is strongly correlated with the maturation of the start-up. It is less an initial choice than a necessity that arises with size, age and the transition to the growth and maturity phases. This observation firmly anchors our conclusions in contingency theory, demonstrating that there is no universal solution, but rather an adaptation of management tools to the organisation's life cycle. However, and this is a major contribution of our study, the role of management control remains paradoxical. In the Moroccan context, it is primarily perceived and utilised as an operational management tool, focusing on performance monitoring and cost control, rather than as a strategic lever for decision-making. The latter remains largely intuitive and centralised around the founder. This observation contradicts traditional theoretical approaches that present management control as a universal instrument of managerial rationalisation. In an emerging context where resources are scarce and the entrepreneurial culture remains highly personal, management control plays a secondary, sometimes symbolic role, serving more to legitimise the company in the eyes of investors and partners than to profoundly transform internal decision-making processes. The study highlights the primary obstacles to implementing management control. These difficulties explain why, in a context of uncertainty and strong financial pressure, start-ups favour simple, flexible and less costly tools.

On a theoretical level, our study shows that the impact of MC in start-ups varies according to the stage of development and the institutional context. Contrary to some studies that emphasise its role as a driver of innovation, in the Moroccan case, it remains primarily a financial tool.

On a practical level, the results suggest a gradual adoption of MC, starting with simple mechanisms and then evolving towards more sophisticated tools.

Although our sample (131 start-ups) provides a robust empirical basis for the Moroccan context, our findings should be applied with caution to other emerging ecosystems. Furthermore, our quantitative approach, based on self-reported data, could be enriched.

Therefore, future research could focus on qualitative or longitudinal studies to analyse in depth how management control practices evolve within a single start-up and why decision-making remains so little influenced by formal tools.

In short, our study reveals that for Moroccan start-ups, management control is not an end in itself, but a means whose relevance and effectiveness depend on its ability to adapt to the complex dynamics of innovation and growth.

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